

Learning Agreement — Host

What are some activities that the visitor will be able to undertake or observe during their visit? Who will support them on the day? What conditions will the visitor have to adhere to in order to do this?

- I will approach this visitor with openness, seeking to facilitate their learning to the best of my ability by providing insights into the working context of my role and organisation.
- I have discussed with the visitor the conditions of their visit, including what information and observations they can and cannot share and how we will ensure that the visit maximises the possible learning in the context of my/my organisation’s needs and obligations.

Host Signature _____

Date _____

Learning Agreement — Visitor

Why are you interested in visiting this particular role or organisation? What do you hope to learn? To what parameters and conditions do you commit?

- I agree to approach this visit with openness, seeking to gain a greater understanding of the working context of the role and organisation I am visiting.
- I agree to be respectful of the organisation which I am visiting, following all applicable policies and procedures and any other conditions agreed with the host.
- I agree to maintain appropriate confidentiality in accordance with the host’s policies and as agreed in advance, with the exception of any observations we agreed I can share with others in my organisation to facilitate broader institutional learning.
- I understand that this visit may be subject to last-minute changes depending on urgent needs of the host or host organisation that may arise at short notice.

Visitor Signature _____

Date _____